

Acontias plumbeus Giant legless skink

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Reptile

Size: 30-50 cm (total body length)

Distribution:

South Africa (Limpopo and Mpumalanga ,extending to coastal KwaZulu-Natal and the Eastern Cape), Eswatini, Mozambique and Zimbabwe (isolated relict populations)

Importance:

Acontias plumbeus, the largest legless skink, is a fossorial species from Southern Africa that supports soil health and invertebrate balance. Genome sequencing could reveal the genetics of limb loss, refine scincid phylogeny, uncover hidden population structure, and support conservation.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 17.93 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 4.83 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 1.82 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: <80%

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 42.48 kilobases

Contig number: 53 477

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